

DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC EXPERTISE IN LINGUISTICS

Toliyeva Shoira

**Assistant, Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Karakalpak State University
ORCID - 0009-0007-3342-7632**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824382>

Abstract: This article describes the specific features of linguistic expertise, which is a new field of applied linguistics. It was also discussed by experts in the field which aspects are of primary importance in dividing linguistic expertise into types.

Key words: applied linguistics, linguistic expertise of regulatory legal documents, special linguistic expertise, legal conclusions, psychological conclusions, forensic linguistic expertise, linguistic knowledge.

Linguistic expertise is of great importance in the development of the system of official work in the state language, in ensuring full compliance with the norms of purely literary language in texts written in an official style, in particular in the texts of documents, as well as in the objective resolution of conflicts related to texts that are products of speech and oral communication. One of the new areas of applied linguistics - the process of linguistic expertise of the products of speech activity (oral and written text) is an important practical research phenomenon from a legal perspective.

Linguistic expertise is the process of conducting research on the formal and substantive analysis of a text based on specific goals, such as checking whether oral or written texts, which are products of human speech activity, comply with the norms of the literary language, providing recommendations for eliminating spelling and stylistic errors, determining what content the lexical units used in the texts express, whether they comply with the requirements of the text, and which object they are directed at, revealing the hidden meaning in the text, determining whether the intended meaning is correctly and clearly reflected in the text, developing recommendations for text editing, and conducting analyses aimed at the legal consequences of the product of speech activity.

In fact, the word expertise is derived from Latin - in Uzbek it means "experienced". The process of expertise is the study of issues that require a qualified solution in one or another field by a specialist or group of specialists. For example, medical expertise, forensic expertise, art expertise, accounting expertise, environmental expertise, etc. The practical or documented result of the expertise is the conclusion of an expert (i.e., specialist) or a group of experts. Although the opinion of an expert (specialist) is not mandatory, disagreement with his opinion must be substantiated in the relevant decisions, conclusions and verdicts. If the expertise is considered incomplete or insufficiently accurate, additional expertise may be assigned. As Uzbek academician Akmal Saidov noted, linguistic expertise is a unique set of knowledge and sciences, and in the scientific and technical development of the whole world this field has risen to the level of a special science. Therefore, leading universities around the world are training specialists in the field of linguistic expertise. Establishing a system for training specialists in the field of linguistic expertise in Uzbekistan is one of the urgent tasks of today.

Many studies have been carried out in the field of linguistic expertise abroad, in particular in Russian linguistics. In particular, in Russian linguistics, many scientific studies by such scientists as Baranov A.N., Brinev K. I., Galyashina E.I., Ivanenko G.S. have been published.

In Uzbek applied linguistics, some regulatory and legal documents have been adopted aimed at linguistic expertise. However, scientific, theoretical and practical research is very scarce. The manual “Linguistic expertise of draft normative and legal documents” by Professor Shukhrat Kochimov, published in 2022 by the Center for Advanced Training of Lawyers under the Ministry of Justice, is the primary practical source in this field.

Linguist A.N. Baranov writes about linguistic expertise: “Linguistic expertise is the process of studying the products of speech activity aimed at identifying important facts and obtaining answers to questions posed to a specialist. Linguistic expertise allows us to determine the truth (falsehood) or possibility (impossibility) of descriptive statements about an object. Linguistic expertise works on the basis of linguistic theories and methods developed in applied linguistics for the study of linguistic objects. Indeed, as a result of linguistic expertise, the level of accuracy and intelligibility of the text (oral or written) in conveying information increases, and many controversial issues related to oral and written texts find their solution.

Linguistic expertise is carried out on oral and written texts that are products of speech activity. The object of expertise can be oral speech, written speech, a complete text, a fragment of a text, a specific lexical unit in the text, a specific phrase in the text, a trademark, and other products of speech activity. Also, such products of speech activity can be presented for linguistic expertise in various forms:

- oral texts (video recordings, audio recordings);
- written texts (books, manuals, translations, manuscripts or printed papers);
- electronic form of oral or written communication on social networks;
- media materials (newspapers, magazines, etc.);
- statements of political or official figures;
- official or informal conversations;
- testimony of impartial witnesses on oral texts, etc.

When a specific material is submitted for linguistic examination, a specific goal is set before the expert. Based on the goal set for the product of speech activity, a linguistic approach is carried out. Linguistic examination can be carried out in a purely linguistic aspect or in legal-linguistic, sociolinguistic, psycholinguistic, pragmalinguistic, ethnolinguistic or other aspects.

When conducting linguistic examination, the qualifications, skills and experience of the expert (specialist) play an important role in ensuring the impartiality, fairness and fairness of the examination. Therefore, a person engaged in linguistic examination is required to be a specialist in his field - applied linguistics, as well as to be aware of the fields of law, psychology, pragmatics, gesture, logic. In most cases, according to the conclusion of linguistic examination, a legal assessment of the process is given, and disputes are resolved based on the substantive interpretation of the oral or written text. In legal proceedings, linguistic expertise can prove the guilt (or innocence) of a suspect. Therefore, linguistic expertise is a very responsible task, requiring a competent and impartial approach from the expert (specialist).

References:

1. Пхомовна, Toliyeva Shoir. "THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE DETERMINATION OF AN OFFENSIVE SITUATION IN A SPECIAL LINGUISTIC EXPERTISE." *ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA FAN VA INNOVATION TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI* 2.16 (2024): 15-19.
2. Аверьянова Т.В. Судебная экспертиза. Курс общей теории: Монография. М.: Норма, Инфра-М, 2015.
3. Пхомовна, Toliyeva Shoir. "ON THE PROBLEM OF LEARNING SOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS." *SCIENCE AND INNOVATION* (2023): 49.
4. Бринев К.И. Судебная лингвистическая экспертиза как отрасль современной прикладной лингвистики. *Вестн. Забайкал. гос.ун-та*. 2009. № 4.
5. Толиева, Шоира Илхомовна. "ЛИНГВИСТИК ЭКСПЕРТИЗА МЕТОДЛАРИНИНГ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ." *Philological research: language, literature, education* 4.4 (2024): 57-59.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY